

WORK TASK MOTIVATION AND INSTRUCTIONAL LEADERSHIP AS PREDICTORS OF TEACHERS PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates influence of work task motivation and instructional leadership to teacher performance among public elementary school teachers. The study employed quantitative research design and the primary tool for data collection is a modified questionnaires of work task motivation, instructional leadership, and teacher performance. The study involved 237 respondents through simple random techniques. The data gathered were subjected to statistical analyses, including mean, correlation, and multiple regression. Research revealed the overall level of work task motivation, instructional leadership and teacher performance is very high. The results also revealed that promoting a highly motivated teacher doing their task alongside strong instructional leadership directly contributes to improved teacher performance. However, specific aspects of work task motivation such as student evaluation, class preparation, and complementary task, stood out as significant predictors of teacher performance, even without a strong emphasis on teaching and administrative tasks. Furthermore, instructional leadership were identified as strong predictors, defining and communicating school goals, play important role in enhancing teacher performance. Thus, it is recommended that future study may explore additional factors that influence teacher performance beyond work task motivation and instructional leadership. While this study identified student evaluation, class preparation, and complementary tasks as key predictors.

Keywords: *Work task motivation, Instructional leadership, Teacher performance, Predictors, School Teacher, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

Teacher performance plays an important part in the overall quality of education, especially to the student's success. However, Agusan del Sur challenges persist due to geographical isolation, limited access to professional development, and a high student-to-teacher ratio (Saro et al., 2025). The ineffectiveness of teachers is an inevitable worldwide phenomenon resulting in several issues for the schools, including low student satisfaction. All these poor teachings produce students with limited learning who lose their civilization's value and may someday burden their country and may affect school's performance, which is influenced by the effectiveness of its teachers (Tjabolo, 2020). With the Department of Education continuously striving to meet quality education standards, investigating these provides an opportunity to identify strengths and address existing challenges. This research particularly aims to influence work task motivation and instructional leadership on teacher performance among public elementary school teachers

Several studies have been conducted to improve the teacher's performance. Globally, studies have stressed the importance of seminar programs in improving teaching practices (Darling-Hammond et al., 2017). Locally, Orale and Ortinero (2020) and Saro et al. (2022) examined the role of instructional leadership and its positive impact on teachers' motivation and classroom management in schools. A study by Chua (2019) revealed that Filipino teachers' effectiveness is closely tied to their access to sufficient teaching resources and administrative support. Accordingly, Singh and Sharma (2021) found that collaborative learning among teachers significantly boosts performance in Indian elementary schools, while Rivera (2020) identified workload and time constraints as barriers to performance among educators. Moreover, Tena and Lopez (2022) argued that community support and involvement are critical in improving teaching outcomes in rural Philippine settings.

In the Philippines, the educational system has made significant strides. The Department of Education (DepEd) set out to meet this issue by ensuring that every person receives meaningful education to help them reach their full potential. While many studies have examined instructional leadership skills of school principals and supervisors, none of them have studied the work task motivation and instructional leadership skills to the performance of teachers based on the perception of the students. It is believed that this study will be important because it is unique, timely, and significant.

Research Objectives

The research aims to identify the influence of work task motivation and instructional leadership on teacher performance among elementary school teachers in Loreto North District, Agusan del Sur. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions.

1. To describe the level of work task motivation of teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1 class preparation;
 - 1.2 teaching;
 - 1.3 evaluation of student;
 - 1.4 administrative task; and
 - 1.5 complementary task.

2. To ascertain the level of instructional leadership of teachers in terms of:
 - 2.1 defining and communicating school goals;
 - 2.2 monitoring and providing feedback on the teaching and learning process; and
 - 2.3 promoting school-wide professional development.
3. To measure the level of teacher performance of teachers in terms of:
 - 3.1 teaching skills;
 - 3.2 management skills;
 - 3.3 disciplinary and regularity; and
 - 3.4 interpersonal relations
4. To determine the significant relationship between the work task motivation and teacher performance
5. To determine which domain in the work task motivation significantly influences the teacher performance.
6. To determine the significant relationship between the instructional leadership and teacher performance.
7. To determine which domain in the instructional leadership that significantly influences the teacher performance.

METHODOLOGY

This research employed a quantitative research design, particularly a descriptive-predictive approach, which would help to identify which domain of work task motivation and instructional leadership influence teacher performance. The study utilized three sets of questionnaires adapted and modified from existing instruments, work tasks motivation from Fernet et al. (2008), instructional leadership from Cayetano (2011), and teacher performance from Amin and Atta (2013). To achieve the reliability of the instruments, it passes through experts who validated it, followed by a pilot test to refine the instrument before distribution, and employed a five-point Likert scale. Data were collected from Loreto North District, Agusan del Sur, comprising 237 respondents. The selection process involved proportional stratified random sampling of targeted students who will rate the performance of their teachers. Statistical analysis, including mean, correlation, and multiple regression, were utilized to analyze the data.

RESULTS

Table 1. Level of Work Task Motivation of Teachers

INDICATORS	Mean	SD	DESCRIPTION
Class Preparation	4.33	0.59	Very High
Teaching	4.37	0.64	Very High
Evaluation of Student	4.30	0.73	Very High
Administrative Task	4.34	0.73	Very High

Complementary Task	4.34	0.70	Very High
Overall	4.34	0.60	Very High

Table 2. Level of Instructional Leadership of Teachers

INDICATORS	Mean	SD	DESCRIPTION
Defining and Communicating School Goals	4.34	0.63	Very High
Monitoring and Providing Feedback on the Teaching and Learning Process	4.17	0.68	High
Promoting School-Wide Professional Development	4.29	0.67	Very High
Overall	4.27	0.62	Very High

Table 3. Level of Teacher Performance

INDICATORS	Mean	SD	DESCRIPTION
Teaching Skills	4.31	0.67	Very High
Management Skills	4.18	0.75	High
Disciplinary and Regularity	4.11	0.83	High
Interpersonal Relations	4.22	0.72	Very High
Overall	4.21	0.66	Very High

Table 4. Significant Relationship between Work Task Motivation and Teacher Performance

Independent Variable	Dependent Variable	r-value	r-square	p-value	Decision
Class Preparation	Teacher Performance	0.698*	0.4872	0.001	Reject H ₀
Teaching		0.670*	0.4489	0.001	Reject H ₀
Evaluation of Student		0.721*	0.5198	0.001	Reject H ₀
Administrative Task		0.667*	0.4449	0.001	Reject H ₀
Complementary Task		0.693*	0.4802	0.001	Reject H ₀

*p<0.05

Table 5. Regression Analysis of the Influence of Work Task Motivation to the Teacher's Performance

Independent Variable	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t-value	p-value	Decision
	β	SE(β)				
Constant	0.463	0.299		2.024	0.044	Reject H ₀
Class Preparation	0.287	0.083	0.254*	3.453	0.001	Reject H ₀
Teaching	0.041	0.088	0.039	0.462	0.644	Failed to Reject H ₀
Evaluation of Student	0.298	0.069	0.328*	4.346	0.001	Reject H ₀
Administrative Task	0.059	0.074	0.065	0.792	0.429	Failed to Reject H ₀
Complementary Task	0.183	0.079	0.192*	2.313	0.022	Reject H ₀

Dependent Variable: Teacher Performance
R = 0.785 R² = 0.616
F-ratio = 62.454 p-value = 0.001

*p<0.05

Table 6. Significant Relationship between Instructional Leadership and Teacher Performance

Independent Variable	Dependent Variable	r-value	r-square	p-value	Decision
Defining and Communicating School Goals	Teacher Performance	0.804*	0.6464	0.001	Reject H ₀
Monitoring and Providing Feedback on the Teaching and Learning Process		0.821*	0.6740	0.001	Reject H ₀
Promoting School-Wide Professional Development		0.799*	0.6384	0.001	Reject H ₀

*p<0.05

Table 7. Regression Analysis of the Influence of Instructional Leadership to the Teacher’s Performance

Independent Variable	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t-value	p-value	Decision
	β	SE(β)				
(Constant)	0.342	0.172				Reject H ₀
Defining and Communicating School Goals	0.312	0.078	0.299*	3.989	0.001	Reject H ₀
Monitoring and Providing Feedback on the Teaching and Learning Process	0.380	0.074	0.388*	5.103	0.001	Reject H ₀
Promoting School-Wide Professional Development	0.216	0.078	0.217*	2.751	0.007	Reject H ₀
Dependent Variable: Teacher Performance						
R = 0.856		R ² = 0.732				
F-ratio = 179.765		p-value = 0.001				

*p<0.05

DISCUSSION

Table 1 presents the work task motivation in elementary school teachers as rated by their students. A mean of 4.34 (very high) indicates that situations concerning the work task motivation are very much observed. Based on the results, all indicators of work task motivation garnered a very high level. Specifically, teaching got the highest rating by students with a mean of 4.37 (very high). This suggests that teachers in public schools deliver education, respond to inquiries, and pay attention to the needs of their students. On the other hand, class preparation got the lowest mean of 4.33 but still garnered a very high. It indicates that public school teachers decide on the subjects and content for the lessons, choosing the presentation formats and order, and developing.

The results above support the study of Ryan and Deci (2000) as cited by Urhahne and Wijnia (2023) that positive motivation towards teaching can be attributed to intrinsic factors such as a sense of purpose, passion for educating young learners, and commitment to student success. According to Mitchell et al. (2020), educators who are happy in their teaching positions are more likely to employ creative teaching strategies, build inclusive classrooms, and build trusting connections with their students—all of which improve learning outcomes. Similarly, evaluation and assessment assist teachers in

tracking students' progress, spotting learning gaps, and modifying their teaching strategies to accommodate a range of student needs (Brookhart, 2013).

Table 2 presents the instructional leadership of elementary school teachers as rated by their students. An overall mean of 4.27 (very high), indicating that situations concerning the instructional leadership are evident at all times. Based on the results, most of the indicators of instructional leadership ranged from a high to a very high level. It can be seen in the table that defining and communicating school goals got the highest mean, while monitoring and providing feedback on the teaching and learning process got the lowest. This implies that educators actively promoted the school's academic objectives to their students, engaged with them, gave them appreciation for their academic achievements, and enhanced their teaching methods.

Based on the study of Hallinger and Heck (2011) as cited by Chen and Guo (2020), when teachers effectively communicate and integrate school goals into their teaching practices, students develop a clearer understanding of academic expectations, fostering a culture of achievement and motivation. Additionally, the promotion of school goals contributes to a positive school culture, where students feel supported and encouraged to reach their full potential (Murphy et al., 2007). While evaluation is a crucial aspect of improving instructional practices, Hallinger and Heck (2011), as cited in Chen and Guo (2020), emphasize that it should be complemented with direct interaction, classroom observations, and collaborative professional development.

Table 3 displays the teacher performance in elementary school teachers as rated by their students. An overall mean of 4.21 (very high), indicating that the situation concerning the teacher performance is excellent. Based on the results, most of the indicators of teacher performance ranged from a high to a very high level. Among its indicators, teaching skills are posited the highest mean of 4.31 (very high), while disciplinary and regularity which is posited lowest mean of 4.11 with a descriptive rating as high level. These results indicate that public school teachers always use different methods of teaching, ensuring that lessons cater to different learning styles and students' needs and fulfill their assigned activities on time.

The study's findings supported the notion that students are more likely to stay engaged when teachers employ a variety of teaching tactics (Darling-Hammond et al., 2020; Pizon & Ytoc, 2022). Tomlinson (2014) highlights that students with different abilities and learning preferences receive appropriate support and are provided with alternative assessment methods. Moreover, Elstad and Christophersen (2017) found that teachers who maintain high levels of professional discipline manage instructional time efficiently and ensure that learning objectives are met and that students receive the necessary support to succeed.

As seen in Table 4, a significant relationship exists between work task motivation and teacher performance, provided that all p-values were less than 0.05. This means that as teachers become more motivated in their tasks, their overall performance improves.

Research shows that teachers who dedicate time to preparing lessons, selecting appropriate teaching materials, and designing student-centered activities achieve better learning outcomes (Stronge, 2018). The findings of Richardson et al. (2014) found out

that teacher motivation leads to improved instructional quality and student academic success. Motivation enhances a teacher's commitment to continuous assessment, ensuring that students receive timely and constructive feedback to support their academic growth (Black & Wiliam, 2009). Moreover, motivated teachers are more likely to collaborate with school administrators, engage in school-wide initiatives, and contribute to the continuous improvement of the educational environment (Runhaar et al., 2013).

Meanwhile, the relationship between work task motivation and teacher performance was shown to be significant, thus, further analysis was made to determine the domain of work task motivation that best predicts teacher performance in public elementary school. The results in Table 5 showed that evaluation of student, class preparation, and complementary task significantly influenced teacher performance, hence it was the best predictor, with t-values of 4.346, 3.453, and 2.313, respectively, and a p-value which is less than the 0.05 level of significance. Moreover, the results revealed that when work task motivation was regressed with teacher performance, it generated an R^2 value of 0.616, which implies that the work task motivation variance can explain 61.6% of the variance of teacher performance among public elementary school teachers.

The results of the study aligned with the findings of Prieto et al. (2023), who analyzed student evaluations of teaching and found that evaluation of the students contributes to improved teacher performance evaluation. Similarly, a study by Cabahug et al. (2024) emphasized the importance of assessment literacy among teachers, linking it to enhanced instructional effectiveness. Additionally, effective classroom preparation ensures that the lesson of teacher is engaging. According to the study of Galache (2024), which highlights that teachers who engage in continuous professional development exhibit improved classroom management and instructional delivery. Furthermore, Galache (2024) found that demographic factors like age and teaching experience influence teachers' engagement in professional development and classroom practices, impacting overall performance.

As shown in Table 6, a significant relationship exists between instructional leadership and teacher performance, provided that all p-values were less than 0.05 level. This means that as instructional leadership strengthens, teacher performance improves.

School leaders who effectively define and communicate school goals provide teachers with a sense of direction and purpose, aligning instructional efforts with institutional objectives. According to Robinson et al. (2008) found that principals who clearly articulate goals and expectations positively influence teacher motivation and instructional practices. Danielson (2013) emphasizes that ongoing evaluation and feedback create a culture of continuous improvement, allowing teachers to adjust their methodologies based on student needs. Moreover, professional development is a key driver of teacher effectiveness and instructional quality. Research by Guskey (2002) indicates that high-quality professional development enhances teacher confidence, skills, and instructional adaptability.

Meanwhile, the relationship between instructional leadership and teacher performance was shown to be significant, thus, further analysis was made to determine the domain of instructional leadership that best predicts teacher performance in public

elementary schools. The results in table 7 revealed that defining and communicating school goals, monitoring and providing feedback on the teaching and learning process, and promoting school-wide professional development, hence it was the best predictor, with a t-values of 3.989, 5.103, and 2.751, respectively and a p-values which is lesser than the 0.05 level of significance. Moreover, the results revealed that when instructional leadership was regressed with teacher performance, it generated an R^2 value of 0.732, which implies that the instructional leadership variance can explain 73.2% of the variance of teachers' performance among public elementary school teachers.

Establishing clear and shared school goals provides direction and aligns the efforts of educators toward common objectives. A study by He et al. (2024) found that instructional leadership is one of the predictors for improving teacher performance through attending seminars. In addition, the studies of Marzano et al. (2005), frequent monitoring and feedback sessions, and guidance from administration can improve teachers' instructional practices.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

The descriptive findings of the study indicate that work task motivation was very much observed in public elementary school teachers in the Municipality of Loreto. Teachers demonstrated a very high level of work task motivation that reflects their dedication and engagement in their profession across various responsibilities, including class preparation, teaching, student evaluation, administrative tasks, and complementary tasks, while instructional leadership is evident in their ability to define and communicate school goals effectively. Teachers exhibited excellent performance, particularly in their teaching skills, reflecting their competence and effectiveness in delivering quality education.

The inferential findings suggest that all indicators of work task motivation and instructional leadership are significantly associated with teacher performance, promoting a highly motivated teacher doing their task alongside strong instructional leadership directly contributes to improved teacher performance. However, when analyzed as a whole, student evaluation, class preparation, and complementary tasks stood out as significant predictors of teacher performance, even without a strong emphasis on teaching and administrative tasks. Furthermore, all indicators of instructional leadership were identified as strong predictors, reinforcing the idea that effective leadership practices, such as defining and communicating school goals, play a crucial role in enhancing teacher performance.

The findings of the study anchored on the Goal Setting Theory emphasize the importance of organizations in setting goals that lead to high performance and motivated employees. This supports the theory wherein the context of education, defining goals in areas of work tasks of the teacher serves as a key driver of their motivation in achieving high standards in their work. Additionally, instructional leadership is important in establishing and communicating these goals, which can lead to teacher satisfaction and increased motivation, thereby becoming effective in their role as a teachers.

Future research may explore additional factors that influence teacher performance beyond work task motivation and instructional leadership. While this study identified student evaluation, class preparation, and complementary tasks as key predictors, other variables may also play a significant role, providing a more holistic understanding of teacher performance.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were proposed, based on the findings of the study.

For educators, it was recommended that educators may actively engage in peer observations, self-assessments, and collaborative discussions to enhance feedback mechanisms and improve instructional leadership practices. It was also recommended that educators participate in mentorship programs and seminars that may provide them with essential skills to give and receive effective feedback.

For school administrators, it was recommended that school administrators may implement targeted training programs focused on maintaining discipline to strengthen teachers' leadership capabilities.

Future studies may explore additional variables that could further explain teacher performance. Researchers are encouraged to broaden the scope of the study by including multiple locations, allowing for a more comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing teacher performance and to verify the results of the present study.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers of this study ensured full compliance with ethical standards in conducting this research. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents before their participation, and they were given the freedom to withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences. The anonymity of all respondents was strictly maintained, and their personal information was kept confidential by data privacy regulations. The well-being of the participants was safeguarded throughout the study, ensuring that no harm, discomfort, or undue pressure was exerted upon them. Furthermore, the researchers affirm that there were no conflicts of interest in the conduct of this study. Plagiarism was strictly avoided, and all sources were properly cited by academic integrity guidelines. The interpretation of the findings was conducted without bias, ensuring objectivity and reliability. The results of this study are used solely for research purposes, contributing to the academic and practical discourse on improving teacher performance.

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REFERENCES

- Amin, M., Shah, R.U., Ayaz, M., & Atta, M.A. (2014). Teachers' Job Performance at Secondary Level in Khyber Pakhyunkhwa, Pakistan.
- Black, P., & William, D. (2009). Developing the theory of formative assessment. *Educational Assessment, Evaluation and Accountability (formerly: Journal of personnel evaluation in education)*, 21, 5-31.
- Brookhart, S. M. (2013). How to create and use rubrics for formative assessment and grading. Ascd.
- Cabahug, I., Osias, N. C., Ongcachuy, B. L., & Corpuz, G. G. (2024). 21st century skills and teachers' performance: Basis for instructional development plan. *American Journal of Arts and Human Science*, 3(2), 82-105.
- Cayetano, J. J. V. (2011). Instructional leadership and student achievement in belizean secondary schools (Order No. 3495852).
- Chen, J., & Guo, W. (2020). Emotional intelligence can make a difference: The impact of principals' emotional intelligence on teaching strategy mediated by instructional leadership. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 48(1), 82-105.
- Chua, P. (2019). The impact of instructional resources on Filipino teachers' effectiveness. *Journal of Education and Technology*, 12(2), 45–56.
- Danielson, C. (2013). The framework for teaching evaluation instrument.
- Darling-Hammond, L., Hyler, M. E., & Gardner, M. (2017). Effective teacher professional development. Learning policy institute.
- Darling-Hammond, L., Flook, L., Cook-Harvey, C., Barron, B., & Osher, D. (2020). Implications for educational practice of the science of learning and development. *Applied developmental science*, 24(2), 97-140.
- Elstad, E., & Christophersen, K. A. (2017). Teachers' self-efficacy at maintaining order and discipline in technology-rich classrooms with relation to strain factors. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 16(1), 103-119.
- Fernet, C., Sénécal, C., Guay, F., Marsh, H., & Dowson, M. (2008). The Work Tasks Motivation Scale for Teachers (WTMST). *Journal of Career Assessment*, 16, 256-279.
- Galache, D. M. (2024). Teachers' professional development, classroom management strategies, and performance. *International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 6(4). <https://doi.org/10.54476/ioer-imrj/391320>
- Guskey, T. R. (2002). Professional development and teacher change. *Teachers and teaching*, 8(3), 381-391.
- Hallinger, P., & Heck, R. H. (2011). Exploring the journey of school improvement: Classifying and analyzing patterns of change in school improvement processes and learning outcomes. *School Effectiveness and School Improvement*, 22(1), 1-27.
- He, P., Guo, F., & Abazie, G. A. (2024). School principals' instructional leadership as a predictor of teacher's professional development. *Asian-Pacific Journal of Second and Foreign Language Education*, 9(1), 63.
- Marzano, R. J. (2005). What we know about teaching for understanding (Review). *Educational Leadership*, 63(2), 48–56
- Mitchell, S. A., Oslin, J. L., & Griffin, L. L. (2020). Teaching sport concepts and skills: A tactical games approach. *Human kinetics*.
- Murphy, J., Elliott, S. N., Goldring, E., & Porter, A. C. (2007). Leadership for learning: A research-based model and taxonomy of behaviors. *School leadership and management*, 27(2), 179-201.
- Orale, R. L., & Ortinero, D. L. (2020). Instructional leadership practices of school heads and teachers' performance: Implications for educational leadership. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 34(4), 789–803.

- Pizon, M. G., & Ytoc, S. T (2022). A Path Model to Infer Mathematics Performance: The Interrelated Impact of Motivation, Attitude, Learning Style and Teaching Strategies Variables. *East Asian Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 1(3), 315-330.
- Prieto, J., Guede-Cid, A., Cid-Cid, A., & Leguey, S. (2023). Major increases in teachers' performance evaluations: Evidence from student evaluation of teaching surveys. *Tuning Journal for Higher Education*, 10(2), 105-125.
- Richardson, P. W., Karabenick, S. A., & Watt, H. M. (2014). *Teacher motivation. Theory and Practice*; Routledge: Hoboken, NJ, USA, 3-36.
- Rivera, L. (2020). Challenges and barriers to effective teaching in Latin American schools. *Education Quarterly Reviews*, 3(1), 35–52
- Robinson, V. M., Lloyd, C. A., & Rowe, K. J. (2008). The impact of leadership on student outcomes: An analysis of the differential effects of leadership types. *Educational administration quarterly*, 44(5), 635-674.
- Runhaar, P., Sanders, K., & Konermann, J. (2013). Teachers' work engagement: Considering interaction with pupils and human resources practices as job resources. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 43(10), 2017-2030.
- Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2000). Self-determination theory and the facilitation of intrinsic motivation, social development, and well-being. *American psychologist*, 55(1), 68.
- Saro, J., Cuasito, R., Doliguez, Z., Maglinte, F., & Pableo, R. (2022). Teaching Competencies and Coping Mechanisms among the Selected Public Primary and Secondary Schools in Agusan del Sur Division: Teachers in the New Normal Education. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 3(10), 969-974.
- Singh, P., & Sharma, K. (2021). Collaborative learning and teacher performance: Evidence from elementary schools in India. *Educational Research for Policy and Practice*, 20(2), 125–141
- Tjabolo, S. A. (2020). The Influence of Teacher Certification on the Performance of Elementary School Teachers in Gorontalo Province, Indonesia. *International Journal of Instruction*, 13(4), 347-360.
- Stronge, J. H. (2018). *Qualities of effective teachers*. Ascd.
- Tena, G., & Lopez, M. (2022). Community involvement in rural education: Improving teacher outcomes in the Philippines. *Asian Journal of Education Research*, 8(4), 102–118.
- Tomlinson, C. A. (2014). *The differentiated classroom: Responding to the needs of all learners*. Ascd.
- Urhahne, D., & Wijnia, L. (2023). Theories of motivation in education: An integrative framework. *Educational Psychology Review*, 35(2), 45.